

Discussion of Diaspora in Bharati Mukherjee's Jasmine

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Bharathi Mukherjee presents the humiliation and pain often associated with third world people adapting to North American culture. In her fiction, Mukherjee depicts problems faced by Indians and other third world immigrants who attempt to assistance into North American lifestyles. So Mukherjee focuses upon sensitive protagonists who lack a stable sense of personal and cultural identity and are victimized by other forms of social operations.

The ‘diaspora’ and ‘identity’ are two words which are always used as contrary to each other. Not only diaspora writers write from “in context” position, but all writers write and speak from a particular place and time, from a history and culture which is specific, Bharati Mukherjee’s earlier writing is full of expatriation and alienation.

Mukherjee’s fiction truly reflects surprising and vital. Mukherjee makes the immigrant characters come so alive that they can most hear their accents and know their ambitions. She decides to immigrate to U.S.A. There she refuses to settle down for the obscurities and dual existence in India and Canada. The immigrant women in the new world come to the entire atmosphere of the past culture and try to balance of past culture with the present one. Her protagonist finds the new country. Where she can forget her past life and lead a new life. Through the portrayal of Jasmine one can also notice Mukherjee’s will to sink into alien culture like that of the united states.

In the novel Jasmine, Bharathi Mukherjee has developed a tale of struggle, violence, wonder, despair, survival and transformation, where the protagonist is delineated through self-reflection, interior monologue, figurative language, narrative pauses and mental blocks. The discussion of Jasmine’s characters, her man-women relationship offers superb avenues to exposure her inner psyche.

Bharathi Mukherjee in her essay has distinctly categorized the two types of American Literary circulation, as “minimalism” and “Maximalism”. In Jasmine the protagonist of Indian origin uprooted from their expatriated and to attempt a new identity. Jasmine is the saga of Jyoti, a young Punjab girl, who wants to fulfil her dead husband, Prakash’s dream of immigrating to America. Jasmine is also a sad story of a young poor Indian girl who lives in the village

of Hasnapur. As the story proceeds the girl constantly changes her names from Jyothi to Jasmine to Jase and to Jane. In this novel the first name Jyothi is married to a city boy from Punjab by name Prakash Viji. Prakash wants his wife to be a modern lady and he prefers to call her Jasmine.

Jasmine is another example of femininity who does not annihilate her ideas and culture to live a new life. She adapts to new life with ease while retaining her old culture. After the death of her husband Jasmine does not commit sati but moves to New York to live out her husband's dream of material success.

A village girl goes alone to America, without job, and husband. She needs the help of her brothers and prepares 'illegal documents' and passport for her transport to America in order to fulfil her husband's dream come true. Unaware of her future difficulties she has to face the problems living alone in America. But Jasmine is encouraged by her late husband from every side of the grief darkened room. She takes with her the statue of a 'Sandalwood Ganapathi', a god with elephant trunks to uproot and difficulty from my path (Jasmine, 102). Jasmine shows herself to be completely different from the other Indian girls.

While traveling in the boat Jasmine meets Half Face, the captain of the boat with one eye and ear who promised to give accommodation to Jasmine promising to be helpful in the beginning. Later he shows his dirty and lustful mind. Jasmine is raped cruelly the day she lands in America. Finally Half Face is murdered by Jasmine and she escapes undetected. She is about to commit suicide but the thought of her mission stopped her. Jasmine is struggling to move out of tortures of physical, mental and emotional along to such an extent that she is driven to violence. Jasmine plans to burn her husband's suit under the palm trees of the college campus and likes to see her lying on the bed of fire in a white sari. But later she denies to death wish and throws all her old values and takes on new identities.

Jasmine is now ready to welcome the prospect of a different life and so she sets out to face the world and the country of her husband's dream.

Mukherjee's move to represent mainstream American culture in terms of "third world" (Jasmine 186) identity must stand in problematic relation to a feminist or "third" (Jasmine, 187) politics of difference. A true "hybrid" (Jasmine, 206) Jyothi to Jasmine, Jasmine to Jase, Jase to Jane reinvented herself with "Jasmine" as her study center. Jasmine provides flower for her hair as she goes to meet Prakash for the first time and "the sweetest smelling Jasmynes" (Jasmine, 89) are the sole decorations at their "No dowry, not guests, Registry office wedding".

She has achieved a new identity only through and with the help of her cultural past. She clearly shows Bharathi Mukherjee's maturity and the interaction between two cultures that lead to love and happiness. Jasmine takes the extreme step of transformation, with a great search for identity in an alien land, and caught between the two cultures of East and West, past and present, old and new with alternating nature of identity of a woman in exile.

Jasmine hopes from place to place and person to person laying to find her place in life; from Jyothi to Jasmine, to Jase and Jane. She travels from Hasnapur to Jullundhur to Florida, Manhattan and Iowa, moving from old world values to the brave new world. Mukherjee's characters have modulated, time to time, through their own personal experiences. The protagonists of earlier novels exhibit a conflict in character. Characters are not able to adjust in the new environment.

It is learnt from Bharathi Mukherjee that women's diasporic consciousness involves diasporic women's social alienation and subordination based on their gender, race and cultural affiliations among others. She traces the conflicts of cultural displacement. Diaspora, on the one hand helps women to enter a new world and meet new people, to practice new culture and adapt to the new atmosphere but on the other it creates many difficulties and troubles to all people especially to women. Mukherjee deals with suffering and struggle in her novel, her vision and approach are totally different. Her

view is not so wide-ranging since she deals with only one aspect, namely, the problem of immigrant 'identity' particularly Asian-Indian, in a white world.

Mukherjee stresses the beliefs and superstitions, rituals and customs embedded in Indian culture. This has not been an easy transition for people to get along with when they live in an alien land.

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